

Proposed Domain-specific Metamodels for MDDPlatform

Adel Vahdati, Raman Ramsin

Department of Computer Engineering, Sharif University of Technology Azadi Avenue, Tehran, Iran
adel.vahdati97@sharif.edu , ramsin@sharif.edu

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This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This document introduces a set of domain-specific metamodels designed for MDDPlatform at different levels of abstraction, including CRAC, CIM, Core Domain, Domain Services, CQRS, API Controllers, Repositories, C# Classes and Interfaces, and Project Settings. Each metamodel captures a perspective necessary to manage complexity in modeling and supports scalable software development.

1. Proposed Domain Specific Languages

Vahdati and Ramsin (Vahdati & Ramsin, 2022) introduced three approaches to manage complexity in modeling. The third approach proposed breaking down the metamodel into several context-specific metamodels instead of creating one large and complicated metamodel. This approach helps manage complexity and eliminates unnecessary details. These context-specific metamodels are referred to as partial metamodels since they cover a part of the overall metamodel. This approach was used in this study to avoid describing a unified metamodel containing unnecessary details (elements and relationships) from specific perspective.

1.1. CRAC Metamodel

The aim of modeling at the CIM level is to explore the problem domain and create analytical models. The first step in this process is to establish a common language between end-users, domain experts, and the development team. As a result, the end-user can describe the problem domain alongside the development team. We proposed a new method called CRAC (Concepts-Responsibilities-Asynchronous Collaboration) to explore the problem domain.

In this method, we first identify domain concepts. Each concept plays a role in the problem domain, and other domain concepts have expectations of it that can be interpreted and expressed in terms of its responsibilities. Carrying out a responsibility by a concept can be accompanied by success or failure. The execution of each responsibility has requirements and its achievement affects the current state of the system and puts it into a new state. On the other hand, a concept can be interested in a set of facts and events within the scope of its responsibilities. Additionally, problem domain concepts can react to an event occurrence.

This method can be conducted in a workshop with the presence of domain experts and the development team or using online tools such as Google Spreadsheet or Miro. In this method, responsibilities are expressed in the form of commands that must be executed, and concept interaction with each other is also done through the publication of events and in an asynchronous manner. To describe this information in the form of a model at the CIM level, we proposed a metamodel called CRAC, which is shown in Figure 1. CRAC metamodel elements are described in Table 1.

Figure 1: CRAC metamodel

Table 1: Introducing the constituent elements of the CRAC metamodel

Name	Type	Description
DomainConcept	Concept	This element represents a concept in the problem domain.
Command	Concept	This element represents a command whose execution causes the system to transition from one valid state to another.
Event	Concept	This element represent the fact that happened due to the execution of a command in the past and is expressed in the form of an event.
isResponsibleFor	Relation	It is the relationship between a domain concept and a command and it shows which concept is responsible for fulfilling a request or handling its execution process.
isInterestedIn	Relation	A relation is between a concept and an event and represents the facts about which a concept is interested in knowing.
publishFact	Relation	It is a relationship between a command and an event and it expresses the fact that established as a result of executing a command.
callForAction	Relation	It is a relationship between an event and a command and it expresses the action that should be taken if an event occurs.

1.2. CIM Metamodel

The purpose of presenting this metamodel at the CIM level is to describe the domain concepts, their properties, the relationships between these concepts, and the functions provided by them. This metamodel is described from three perspectives: DomainConcept, ValueObject, and Operation. In this metamodel, instead of using primitive types such as string, we defined a new concept called ‘StringValueObject’ to describe constraints on the values of these properties. This allows for constraints on the values of properties to be described, such as whether a string can be empty or null, has a length constraint, or a specific format. These details are shown separately in Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5 to improve readability and described in Table 2.

Figure 2: A partial metamodel of CIM from DomainConcept perspective

Figure 3: A partial metamodel of CIM form ValueObject perspective

Figure 4: A partial metamodel of CIM from Operation perspective

Figure 5: Describing property value constraints

Table 2: The constituent elements of the CIM metamodel

Name	Type	Description
DomainConcept	Concept	This element represents a concept in the problem domain.
Operation	Concept	This element represents an operation of a concept.
ValueObject	Concept	This element describes a composite value object, consisting of several primitive value objects.
StringValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes string attribute.
IntegerValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes an integer attribute.
LongValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a numeric attribute of type 'long'
BooleanValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a logical attribute.
DateTimeValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a date time attribute.
GuidValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes the globally unique identifier (GUID) attribute.
Relation	Concept	This element describes the destination (target) of a relationship from the relation owner perspective (source) using three attributes: 'RelationName', 'RelationTarget', and 'Multiplicity'.
Parameter	Concept	This element describes the input parameter of the operation
StringParameter	Concept	This element describes a string parameter.
IntegerParameter	Concept	This element describes an integer parameter.
LongParameter	Concept	This element describes a 'long' type parameter.
BooleanParameter	Concept	This element describes a logical parameter.
DateTimeParameter	Concept	This element describes a date time parameter.
GuidParameter	Concept	This element describes a globally unique identifier parameter.
hasProperty	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between a concept and its value object attributes.
hasOperation	Relation	This element represents the relationship between a concept and its operations.
hasRelation	Relation	This element associate a concept (source of a relation) with the 'Relation' element that describe the destination (target) of that relation.
hasListOf	Relation	This element represents the relation between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values is important, but duplicates are allowed.
hasSetOf	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values does not matter, and duplicates are not allowed.
hasInput	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an operation and its inputs.

1.3. Core Domain Metamodel

The goal of this metamodel is to provide an abstract way to describe the core domain concepts. The metamodel is described from several perspectives (context), including: 'Aggregate' (Figure 6), 'BaseEntity' (Figure 7), 'ValueObject' (Figure 8), 'Operation' (Figure 9), 'Command' (Figure 10), and 'Event' (Figure 11). These partial metamodels may overlap with each other, but there may be a concept in a metamodel that is not needed in another one because it is not necessary to describe the problem from that perspective.

Additionally, in two partial metamodels, there may be a common concept with different level of details. For example, from the perspective of 'Aggregate', it is important to model its constituent entities, but at this level of modeling, we do not have the concern of what features each entity has, so we do not need to model 'BaseEntity' attributes from 'Aggregate' point of view. However, when we want to model the core domain metamodel from the perspective of 'BaseEntity', we need to model the attributes of each entity. Therefore, describing the core domain metamodel from

different perspectives leads to the defining several context-specific partial metamodels that, although they may overlap, each have separate concerns. The constituent elements of core domain metamodel are described in Table 3.

Figure 6: Partial metamodel of core domain from ‘Aggregate’ perspective

Figure 7: Partial metamodel of core domain from ‘BaseEntity’ perspective

Figure 8: Partial metamodel of core domain from 'ValueObject' perspective

Figure 9: Partial metamodel of core domain form 'Operation' perspective

Figure 10: Partial metamodel of core domain from 'Command' perspective

Figure 11: Partial metamodel of core domain from 'Event' perspective

Table 3: The constituent elements of core domain metamodel

Name	Type	Description
Aggregate	Concept	This element represents a set of one or more entities and value objects that maintain data consistency and enforce invariants.
BaseEntity	Concept	This element represents an entity with a unique identifier.
ValueObject	Concept	This element describes a composite value object, consisting of several primitive value objects.
StringValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes string attribute.
IntegerValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes an integer attribute.
LongValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a numeric attribute of type 'long'
BooleanValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a logical attribute.
DateTimeValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a date time attribute.
GuidValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes the globally unique identifier (GUID) attribute.
Operation	Concept	This element represents an operation of a concept.
Parameter	Concept	This element describes the input parameter of the operation
StringParameter	Concept	This element describes a string parameter.
IntegerParameter	Concept	This element describes an integer parameter.
LongParameter	Concept	This element describes a 'long' type parameter.
BooleanParameter	Concept	This element describes a logical parameter.
DateTimeParameter	Concept	This element describes a date time parameter.
GuidParameter	Concept	This element describes a globally unique identifier parameter.
Command	Concept	This element represents a command whose execution causes the system to transition from one valid state to another.
Event	Concept	This element expresses the fact that happened due to the execution of a command in the past and is expressed in the form of an event.
hasRoot	Relation	This element is a relationship that indicate the primary 'BaseEntity' of an 'Aggregate' that enforces business rules and invariants.
hasEntityID	Relation	This element is a relationship between an entity and one or more attributes that together form the entity's unique identifier.
hasProperty	Relation	This element represents the relationship between a concept and its attributes.
hasListOf	Relation	This element represents the relation between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values is important, but duplicates are allowed.
hasSetOf	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values does not matter, and duplicates are not allowed.
hasOperation	Relation	This element represents the relationship between a concept and its operations.
hasInput	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an operation and its inputs.

1.4. Domain Service Metamodel

The purpose of this metamodel is to provide an abstract syntax that can be used to describe the domain services. This metamodel is described from the following perspectives: Service (Figure 12), Interface (Figure 13), and Operation (Figure 14).

Figure 12: Partial metamodel of domain service from 'Service' perspective

Figure 13: Partial metamodel of domain service from 'Interface' perspective

Figure 14: Partial metamodel of domain service from 'Operation' perspective

The reason why the domain service metamodel is described in terms of ‘Interface’ and ‘Operation’ instead of ‘Repository’ depends on the purpose of the metamodel and whether we need the details from a specific perspective. Since a service implements an interface and the operations provided by an interface affect the structure and operations of the service, we need to describe the metamodel from the perspective of ‘Interface’ and ‘Operation’. On the other hand, the structure and attributes of the repository do not affect the structure and attributes of the service, so we do not need to describe it at this level of modeling. The only relevant information is which repositories a service needs as a collaborator, which is expressed from the perspective of the ‘Service’ concept. The constituent elements of domain service metamodel are described in Table 4.

Table 4: The constituent elements of domain service metamodel

Name	Type	Description
Service	Concept	This element describe the concept of service and includes a set of functions that can be used by other concepts.
Interface	Concept	This element describe the concept of interface.
Repository	Concept	This element represents the concept of repository that facilitates data storage and retrieval.
Operation	Concept	This element represents an operation that a service or an interface provides.
Parameter	Concept	This element describes the input parameter of the operation
StringParameter	Concept	This element describes a string parameter.
IntegerParameter	Concept	This element describes an integer parameter.
LongParameter	Concept	This element describes a ‘long’ type parameter.
BooleanParameter	Concept	This element describes a logical parameter.
DateTimeParameter	Concept	This element describes a date time parameter.
GuidParameter	Concept	This element describes a GUID (globally unique identifier) parameter.
hasCollaborator	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between a service and other concepts whose collaboration is necessary to achieve the goals.
realizeInterface	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between a service and the interfaces realized by it.
hasOperation	Relation	This element represents the relationship between a concept and its operations.
hasInput	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an operation and its inputs.

1.5. CQRS Pattern Metamodel

The goal of this metamodel is to provide an abstract syntax for describing design in the form of the CQRS pattern. This metamodel is described from the following perspectives: ‘CommandHandler’ (Figure 15), ‘QueryHandler’ (Figure 16), ‘EventHandler’ (Figure 17), ‘Command’ (Figure 18), ‘Event’ (Figure 19), and ‘Query’ (Figure 20). The constituent elements of CQRS pattern metamodel are described in Table 5.

Figure 15: The CQRS pattern partial metamodel from 'CommandHandler' perspective

Figure 16: The CQRS pattern from 'EventHandler' perspective

Figure 17: The CQRS pattern partial metamodel from 'QueryHandler' perspective

Figure 18: The CQRS pattern partial metamodel from 'Command' perspective

Figure 19: The CQRS pattern partial metamodel from 'Event' perspective

Figure 20: The CQRS pattern partial metamodel from 'Query' perspective

Table 5: The constituent elements of CQRS pattern metamodel

Name	Type	Description
CommandHandler	Concept	This element represents the handler of a command.
Command	Concept	This element represents a command whose execution causes the system to transition from one valid state to another.
EventHandler	Concept	This element represents the event handler.
Event	Concept	This element represent the fact that happened due to the execution of a command in the past and is expressed in the form of an event.
QueryHandler	Concept	This element represents the handler of the query.
Query	Concept	This element represents a query request to obtain the required information.
QueryResult	Concept	This element represents the result of a query.
Interface	Concept	This element represents the concept of interface.
Service	Concept	This element represents a service whose functions can be used by other concepts.
Repository	Concept	This element represents the data repository that is responsible for storing and retrieving data.
ValueObject	Concept	This element describes a composite value object, consisting of several primitive value objects.
StringValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes string attribute.
IntegerValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes an integer attribute.
LongValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a numeric attribute of type 'long'
BooleanValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a logical attribute.
DateTimeValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes a date time attribute.
GuidValueObject	Concept	This element is a primitive value object that describes the globally unique identifier (GUID) attribute.
hasCollaborator	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a concept and the collaborators whose cooperation is necessary to realize the goals of that concept.
canHandle	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a command handler and a command, an event handler and an event, or a query handler and a query.
canPublish	Relation	This element specifies the relationship between a command handler and the event emitted by the command.
return	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a query and the result of that query.
hasProperty	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a concept and its property.

1.6. API Controller Metamodel

The goal of this metamodel is to provide an abstract syntax to describe the entry point of web requests into a system and distribute them in the form of a controller pattern. This metamodel is described from two perspectives: the 'ApiController' (Figure 21) perspective and the 'DTO' (Figure 22) perspective. The constituent elements of API Controller metamodel are described in Table 6.

Figure 21: The partial metamodel from ApiController perspective

Figure 22: The partial metamodel from DTO perspective

Table 6: The constituent elements of API Controller metamodel

Name	Type	Description
ApiController	Concept	This element represents the concept of web API controller.
Endpoint	Concept	This element is an abstract concept and represents an endpoint on the server side to which requests are sent to call functionalities provided by the web services.
HTTPPost	Concept	This element represents the method of sending a POST request in the HTTP protocol.
HTTPGet	Concept	This element represents the method of sending a GET request in the HTTP protocol.
HTTPDelete	Concept	This element represents the method of sending a DELETE request in the HTTP protocol.
HTTPPut	Concept	This element represents the method of sending a PUT request in the HTTP protocol.
HTTPPatch	Concept	This element represents the method of sending a PATCH request in the HTTP protocol.
Interface	Concept	This element represents the concept of interface.
Service	Concept	This element represents a service whose functions can be used by other concepts.
Command	Concept	This element represents a command whose execution causes the system to transition from one valid state to another.
Query	Concept	This element represents a query request to obtain the required information.
DTO	Concept	This element is a data structure used to exchange information.
StringParameter	Concept	This element describes a string parameter.
IntegerParameter	Concept	This element describes an integer parameter.
LongParameter	Concept	This element describes a 'long' type parameter.
BooleanParameter	Concept	This element describes a logical parameter.
DateTimeParameter	Concept	This element describes a date and time parameter.
GuidParameter	Concept	This element describes a GUID (globally unique identifier) parameter.
hasEndpoint	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between an ApiController and its endpoints.
hasCollaborator	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between a concept and the cooperating components whose collaborations are necessary to realize the goals of that concept.
dispatchCommand	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an ApiController and a command, that the controller is responsible for dispatching it to the appropriate handler.
dispatchQuery	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an ApiController and a query, that the controller is responsible for dispatching it to the appropriate handler.
hasRouteParameter	Relation	This element describes the relationship between the endpoint and the access rout parameters.
hasRequestBody	Relation	This element is the relationship between the endpoint and the data that is packaged and sent in the body of the request.
hasQueryParameter	Relation	This element is the relationship between an endpoint and the data sent as query parameters with the request.
return	Relation	This element describes the relationship between the HTTPGet concept and the DTO concept, and represents the structure of the returned information
hasProperty	Relation	This element represents the relationship between a concept and its attributes.
hasListOf	Relation	This element represents the relation between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values is important, but duplicates are allowed.
hasSetOf	Relation	This element represent the relationship between a concept and its multi-valued attribute, where the order of the values does not matter, and duplicates are not allowed.

1.7. Repository Pattern Metamodel

The aim of this metamodel is to offer a general way of explaining how data is stored, updated, retrieved, and deleted using the repository pattern. It outlines the repository pattern from two perspective: the 'Database' concept (Figure 23) and the 'Repository' (Figure 24) concept. The constituent elements of Repository pattern metamodel are described in Table 7.

Figure 23: Partial metamodel of Repository pattern from 'Database' perspective

Figure 24: Partial metamodel of Repository pattern from 'Repository' perspective

Table 7: The constituent elements of Repository pattern metamodel

Name	Type	Description
Repository	Concept	This element represents the concept of the Repository.
Aggregate	Concept	This element represents a set of one or more entities and value objects that maintain data consistency and enforce invariants.
CRUD	Concept	This element is an abstract concept that represents the operations of creating, retrieving, updating and deleting an entity.
CreateEntity	Concept	This element represents the operation of creating an entity in the repository.
DeleteEntity	Concept	This element represents the operation of removing an entity from the repository.
UpdateEntity	Concept	This element represents the update operation of an entity in the repository.
GetEntity	Concept	This element represents the operation of retrieving an entity from the repository.
ListEntity	Concept	This element represents the operation of retrieving a set of entities from the repository.
Database	Concept	This element represents the concept of database.
DataEntity	Concept	This element represents the concept of data entity.
Property	Concept	This element represents the attributes of the data entity.
Parameter	Concept	This element describes the input parameter of the operation
StringParameter	Concept	This element describes a string parameter.
IntegerParameter	Concept	This element describes an integer parameter.
LongParameter	Concept	This element describes a 'long' type parameter.
BooleanParameter	Concept	This element describes a logical parameter.
DateTimeParameter	Concept	This element describes a date time parameter.
GuidParameter	Concept	This element describes a globally unique identifier parameter.
hasOperation	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the concept of Repository and its operations.
return	Relation	This element represent the relationship between the 'GetEntity' concept and the 'Aggregate' concept, and indicates the type of returned entity.
returnListOf	Relation	This element represent the relationship between the concept of 'ListEntity' and the 'Aggregate' concept, and indicates the type of the set of returned entities.
hasParameter	Relation	This element represent the relationship between an operation of the repository and its input parameters.
hasCollaborator	Relation	This element represent the relationship between the concept of repository and database.
hasSetOf	Relation	This element represent the relationship between the database and the data entities.
hasProperty	Relation	This element represent the relationship between the data entity and its attributes.

1.8. C# Class and Interface Metamodel

The goal of this metamodel is to provide an abstract syntax that allows describing the solution domain with the use of class and interface concepts in the C# programming language. This metamodel is described from the following perspectives: BaseClass (Figure 25), Constructor (Figure 26), Operation (Figure 27), and Interface (Figure 28). The constituent elements of C# class and interface metamodel are described in Table 8.

Figure 25: The partial metamodel form 'BaseClass' perspective

Figure 26: The partial metamodel form 'Constructor' perspective

Figure 27: The partial metamodel from 'Operation' perspective

Figure 28: Partial metamodel from ‘Interface’ perspective

Table 8: The constituent elements of C# class and interface metamodel

Name	Type	Description
BaseClass	Concept	This element represents the concept of class.
Property	Concept	This element represents the class property.
Field	Concept	This element represents the fields defined in the class.
Constructor	Concept	This element represents the constructor of the class.
Interface	Concept	This element represents the concept of interface.
Package	Concept	This element represents the software package whose functions are used inside the class.
Operation	Concept	This element represents the class operation.
OperationBody	Concept	This element represents the body of the operation.
Parameter	Concept	This element represents the input parameters of the operation or class constructor.
hasProperty	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the class and its properties.
hasField	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the class and its fields.
hasConstructor	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the class and its constructor.
hasOperation	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between the class and its operation, or the interface and its operation.
usePackage	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the class and the software package that is used.
realizeInterface	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the class and the interfaces that is implemented.
hasPropertyValue	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the constructor and a parameter that contains the initial value of a property with the same name and type in the class.
hasFieldValue	Relation	This element represents the relationship between the constructor and a parameter that contains the initial value of a field with the same name and type in the class.
hasBody	Relation	This element represents the relationship between an operation and its body.
extend	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between an interface and other interfaces that it inherits from.

1.9. Project Setting and Dependency Metamodel

The purpose of this metamodel is to provide an abstract syntax for describing the settings and configuration of a software project in the .NET framework, which is described from two perspectives: Project (Figure 29) and AppSettings (Figure 30). The constituent elements of project settings and dependency metamodel Table 9.

Figure 29: Partial metamodel from 'Project' perspective

Figure 30: The partial metamodel from 'AppSettings' perspective

Table 9: The constituent elements of project settings and dependency metamodel

Name	Type	Description
Project	Concept	This element represents the software project that implemented the solution to the problem.
PackageReference	Concept	This element describes the software libraries used in solving the problem.
ProjectReference	Concept	This element describes other software projects used in the solution.
AppSettings	Concept	This element represents the settings of the application.
Config	Concept	This element represents configuration information expressed in key-value format.
hasDependency	Relation	This element describes the relationship between the software project and the software libraries used.
hasReference	Relation	This element describes the relationship between the software project and other projects that are used.
hasSettings	Relation	This element describes the relationship between the software project and the application settings.
hasConfig	Relation	This element describes the relationship between application settings and configuration information.

1.10. Project Code Metamodel

At the Code level, a simple metamodel is presented to model the structure of the project, its constituent folders and files, and the content of each file. The details of this metamodel described in Figure 31 and Table 10.

Figure 31: Project code metamodel

Table 10: The constituent elements of project code metamodel

Name	Type	Description
Project	Concept	This element represents the software project that implemented the solution to the problem.
ProjectFolder	Concept	This element represents the concept of folder in the project structure.
ProjectFile	Concept	This element represents the concept of file in the project structure.
hasFolder	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between the project and its folders or the relationship of a folder with its subfolders.
hasFile	Relation	This element expresses the relationship between the project and the project files or the relationship between a folder and the files inside it.

References

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